

The Impact of Social Networking Sites on Family Relations from the Point of View of Parents of Students in the City of Sahab/Jordan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 11, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 12, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Family Relationships, Social Networking Sites, Parents</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5501920</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to identify the impact of social networking sites on family relationships from the point of view of parents of students in Sahab city during the first semester of the academic year (2020/2021). The study sample consisted of (864) families chosen at random from the study population of (36,475) parents. The researcher used a questionnaire with (27) items divided into three domains, and the validity and reliability of the two study tools were verified, as the value of the (alpha) coefficient of the questionnaire's total reliability was (0.88). In order to identify the results of the study, the following statistical treatments were used: t-test for independent samples, One-way analysis of variance, and calculating the frequencies of the reality of family relationships. The study showed several results, the most important of which are: - There are statistically significant differences according to the income variable, in favor of the higher income, and the study did not find differences due to the variables of gender, qualification, age and number of family members. The researcher recommended the need to remove barriers between parents and children, which helps children from their parents' experiences in life and guide them in order to overcome the psychological difficulties they encounter in their daily lives.</i></p>

Introduction

The contemporary world has witnessed a set of rapid changes in the field of communication and information technology, which has made the world a global village in which information is transmitted to all parts of the globe in fractions of a second, and there is no doubt that these changes have a direct impact on individuals and institutions, societies are motivated by accepting these innovations and adapting to them in order to benefit from the advantages they offer in all fields (Al-Shahri,2011).

Online social networking sites, the most famous of all, Facebook and Twitter, are among the latest and most popular communications technology products. Although these sites were originally established for social communication between individuals, their use extended to include political activity through the circulation of information on political events as well as invitation to attend seminars or demonstrations. And the beginning of the emergence of social sites was in the mid-nineties, when Classmates.com was established in 1995 to link between classmates and SixDegrees.com in 1997, which focused on direct links between people, and on those sites appeared user profiles and a private messaging service for a group of friends (Khaled, 2008).

And electronic networking sites are the most prevalent on the Internet because of the characteristics they have that distinguish them from other websites, which encouraged Internet surfers from all over the world to increase their demand despite the severe criticism that social networks are always subjected to, from these criticisms the negative and direct impact On the family society and its disintegration, but on the other hand, there are those who see it as an important means for growth and cohesion between societies, bringing concepts and visions closer with the other, and getting acquainted with the cultures of different peoples, in addition to its active and distinguished role as an effective means of communication in and mass uprisings (Al Mansour, 2012).

In this regard, electronic communication networks constitute a subject in which two different theses collide. The first thesis sees in these sites an opportunity for humanity to exchange communication and knowledge and to eliminate the obstacles of time and space, thus increasing people's rapprochement, raising the degree of their interaction and establishing new social relations, it also reduces a huge amount of procedures in commercial and economic transactions and exchanges, while the second thesis considers these networks a catastrophic view, as it considers that they constitute the source of the real danger to social relations, and lead to the birth of a society that carries factors of estrangement with cultural traditions, as well as leads to isolation and disintegration of the fabric of social life. They believe that social media has invaded family life, reducing opportunities for interaction and communication within the family (Bushleibi, 2006)

The Problem of the Study

On the basis that the family is the basic nucleus in building society through its influence in raising children and the source of morals and values and the first pillar for controlling the normal behavior of individuals, and as a result of the researchers' observation and experience of many effects caused by modern means of communication and communication on the values and morals of our young children and adolescents, including those who spend a lot of time in what is known as chat, and getting to know the most prominent scandals of some social, cultural and other personalities, and sending them and circulating them among themselves, so the child finds himself falling prey in the fishing net of these sites to polish his personality and gain him ideas and beliefs that were not accepted in our society in the past, but now they have become an integral part of it, and parents can no longer impose their opinion on their children to raise them properly, or to punish them for inappropriate behavior, because - even if they find a little time for that - they find that they need days or more to modify these behaviors, so they withdraw and leave the space again for these sites to spoil the minds of young people.

This was confirmed by Nisreen Darzi in her article in Al-Ittihad newspaper (social networking sites...Deaf screens that kill family dialogue): Modern family sessions are no longer enjoying the simplicity and familiarity that they used to have previously, and the main dilemma lies in surrendering to this phenomenon that sweeps homes and robs them of their family atmosphere which is based on dialogue, consultation, and enjoyment together, even if it is by watching a television program.

Therefore, the researcher believes that it is a big problem that deserves a scientific study, in order to find a solution to this problem, which is to answer the main question of the study: What is the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab / Jordan.

The Questions of the Study

The study attempted to answer the following main question:

What is the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab / Jordan.

The following sub-questions emerged:

1. Does the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites differ from the point of view of parents of students in Sahab city according to the gender of the parent?
2. Does the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites differ from the point of view of the students' parents in Sahab city according to the educational qualification?
3. Does the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites differ from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab according to age?
4. Does the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites differ from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab according to the family's income?
5. Does the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites differ from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab according to the number of family members?

The Study Hypotheses

This study sought to test the following null hypotheses:

The first hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in Sahab city according to the gender of the guardian.

The second hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in the city of Sahab according to the educational qualification.

The third hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in the city of Sahab according to age.

The fourth hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in Sahab city according to the family's income.

The fifth hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in the city of Sahab according to the number of family members.

The Objectives of the Study

This study sought to identify:

1. The level of family relations resulting from social networking sites in the city of Sahab.

2. The level of using the social network from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab.
3. The extent of the effectiveness of social communication from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab according to the variables of gender, educational qualification, age, income, number of family members.
4. The reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab according to the variables of gender, educational qualification, age, income, number of family members.
5. The strength of the relationship in the effectiveness of social communication from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab according to the variables of gender, educational qualification, age, income, number of family members.

The Significance of the Study

At the beginning of every invention there is a rejection by society of such an invention, and with the passage of time some people become convinced of the importance of this invention, and this defense arises that generates conflict, which is called in science the cultural conflict, this is what happened with the invention of social networking sites. Hence, the importance of this study stems from directing the attention of officials towards the negative impact that social networking sites have had on the relationship of fathers with children, and towards investing in them in the interest of society, and what strengthens family relationships. Through this study, we aspire to provide parents and children with the information and recommendations necessary to improve family relations and make positive use of social networking sites. The importance of this study is summarized in the following:

- This study is complementary to the various studies that seek to reveal the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites.
- Shedding more light on the issue of social networking sites and their effects on the family; With a view to developing remedial and advisory programs by the institutions and the competent authorities in the governorate, to mitigate the effects of these problems.
- Benefiting from the results of this study from the theoretical and practical perspectives; In theory, it will help determine the results of the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites. As for the practical aspect, it will develop appropriate treatment programs that will strengthen family relations and enhance the relationship of all members of society with each other.

Definition of the Study Terms

The family: it is a group of people linked by marriage or blood ties, and they form one home, and interact with each other within the framework of specific social roles, such as husband, wife, father, mother, son, daughter, brother, and sister (Al-Awaidi, 2004, p. 98). The researcher points out that the family is the basic category of society, and it includes the father and the mother, who are the basis, so this category is formed, and what is called family relationships are established between them based on the relationships of fathers with children, and the relationship of children with fathers.

Family social relations: It means those relationships that exist between the roles of the husband, wife and children, and (also) the nature of communications and interactions that occur between family members who reside in one house, and from that relationship that occurs between the husband and wife, and between the children themselves. The urban family is considered an extended and patriarchal family, and it is characterized by the dominance of men over women, as well as adults over children, so there is a hierarchical distribution of power, and power is in the hands of men (Abdul Hakim, 2012, p. 36). The researcher points out that family social relations are the ties that bring together members of the same family under one roof, to meet the family's needs and desires, and the father and mother are the basic building blocks in its formation, and they do their utmost to take care of their children.

Social networking sites: It is a system of electronic networks that allow the subscriber to create his own site, and then link it through an electronic social system with other members who have the same interests and hobbies, as electronic social networking sites have recently become dominating the times and ideas of young people (Al Alami, 2011, p. 34). The researcher points out that social networking sites are a group of websites that society members use to communicate with each other and form social relationships of various kinds from different countries of the world, and these relationships have become an alternative to real family and social relationships.

Parents of the students: They are all parents who represent the parents of the students and have responded to all the items of the questionnaire from inside the city of Sahab.

Previous Studies

The researcher reviewed some studies that tackled social media

Al-Homsi (2010) conducted a study entitled "Internet addiction among young people and its relationship to social communication skills", and it was applied at the University of Damascus on (150) male and female students (36) females and (114) males from various scientific disciplines and different economic conditions, and the study aimed to shed light on the phenomenon of Internet addiction and its relationship to social communication skills and knowledge of the differences in Internet addiction according to variables (gender, economic status, scientific specialization), the researcher relied on the descriptive analytical approach, and the research tools consisted of (a scale for Internet addiction and a scale for social relations), and the study concluded:

- There is a statistically significant correlation between Internet addiction and social communication skills. Sitting for long periods of Internet use makes the individual dedicate less time to other activities.
- That females relate to the use of the Internet more than males and this is due to the nature of female socialization in our societies.
- There are no statistically significant differences in Internet addiction with the change and different economic status of individuals, and this is due to the cost of using the Internet available to everyone.

Vansoon (2010) conducted a study entitled "The Impact of Using Technology on Social Relationships", and it was applied to a sample of (1600) young users of social networks in Britain, which aimed to identify the impact of the use of social networks on social relations, and the researcher used the method Analytical descriptive and questionnaire tool for collecting information. The study reached several results, the most important of which are:

- More than half of adults who use sites including (Facebook and YouTube) have admitted that they spend more time on the Internet than with their real friends or family members.
- The study also showed that they talk less on the phone and do not watch much television, and that electronic communication networks have changed the lifestyle of (53%) of the sample.

Amin (2009) conducted a study entitled "The Limits of Social Interaction in Virtual Communities on the Internet", and it was applied to two types of virtual communities on the Internet, first: those virtual communities that are based on cultural and social interaction, and the exchange of ideas and opinions through sites that allow their users to add, comment and participate Active activities such as: (forums, blogs, chat rooms, Facebook), the second type is the complete virtual communities on the web, which are websites that try to simulate the real world by providing a number of multiple options for users to enable them to practice the details of their lives as if they were in the real world, from buying, selling, wearing clothes, traveling by planes, and others such as: (Second Life) , google lively community), this study aimed to identify the patterns of virtual communities on the Internet and the general features that distinguish each pattern, and the limits of what it can offer in terms of social and cultural interactions among the residents of these communities. Scientific observation was used and the qualitative content analysis of some virtual communities on the Internet, and the study found:

- There are a number of factors that affect virtual societies positively or negatively, including the extent of consistency or difference with prevailing values and beliefs, and the extent to which they adopt constructive communication patterns that contribute to the development of real life.
- Social networking such as Facebook reshaped the relationship between the different systems in society, and added new dimensions of social communication between individuals within the system, as well as used to mobilize geographically and ideologically dispersed masses to pressure political systems to demand more rights and express full freedom of opinions and beliefs.

Bellamy and Hanewicz (2001) conducted a study entitled "The Social and Psychological Effects of Internet Addiction" on (114) male and female students in the US state of Michigan, and it aimed to know the effect of the Internet in creating a state of addiction among its users. The researchers used two scales for this purpose, a quantitative measure based on the amount of time young people spend in chat rooms on the Internet, and another four-item scale that measures the degree of Internet orientation. The study found that young people's orientation towards the Internet and their addiction to it is related to gender and some personal variables such as control, social acceptance, and personal relationships of the respondents.

The Study Methodology

This study is a type of descriptive studies. It describes the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab.

The Study Population and Its Sample

The study population consisted of parents in the city of Sahab, which numbered (36,475) families, who were chosen by random method. The study was conducted on a sample of (864) families. Table (1) shows the characteristics of the study sample members.

Table 1: Distribution of study sample members according to the variables of gender, educational qualification, age, income, number of family members

Variable	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	400	%46.29
	Female	464	%53.70
	Total	864	%100
Scientific qualification	Tawjihi or less	322	%37.26
	Diploma	176	%20.36
	Bachelor	280	%32.40
	Master's degree and above	86	%9.95
	Total	864	%100
Age	25_20	78	%9.02
	30_26	114	%13.19
	35_31	242	%28.00
	36 and above	430	%49.76
	Total	864	%100
Income	1500 or less	176	%20.37
	2500_1500	310	%35.87
	3500_2501	204	%23.61
	More than 3500	172	%19.907
	Total	864	%100
The number of family members	4 or less	242	%28.009
	6_4	400	%46.29
	More than 6	222	%25.69
	Total	864	%100

The Study Tools

After reviewing a number of previous studies, such as the Nomar study (2012) and the Al-Owaidi study (2004), he developed a tool to achieve the objectives of the study, which is the Parents Questionnaire, which is directed to all families in Sahab Governorate, and the number of its items reached (27) items distributed into three areas. The questionnaire, in its final form, consisted of two parts:

1. The first section: contains the personal data of the study sample.
2. The second section: consists of (27) items divided into four areas as follows:
 - The first domain: family relations, and it consists of (11) items, the items (2,4,5,6,11) were positive, while items (1,3,7,8,9,10) were negative.
 - The second domain: cultural, and it consists of (7) items. Items (12,13,14,16,17,18) was positive, while item (15) was negative.
 - The third domain: psychological, and it consists of (7) items, and the items (20,22,23,24) were positive, while items (19,21,25,26,27) were negative.

The response to the questionnaire items was based on a five-dimensional Likert scale. The items were built, and the weights were given as follows:

Category	Somewhat applicable				
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
points	5	4	3	2	1

So that the correction scale was reversed in the negative paragraphs.

The validity of the study tools

The researcher made sure of the validity of the study tool from arbitrators with experience and competence, who are members of the teaching staff in the faculties of educational sciences in Jordanian universities; The arbitrators confirmed that the tool is valid after deleting some items, and modifying others.

The researcher distributed the questionnaire to the sample, and it was present, and no inquiries were made during the application, and it was implemented easily, and the validity was also verified by calculating the correlation matrix of the tool's items with the total score and the table (2) illustrates this.

Table 2: Correlation matrix of tool items with the total score

Item	t-value	Sig	Item	t-value	Sig
1	0.47	0.000	16	0.52	0.000
2	0.59	0.000	17	0.46	0.000
3	0.47	0.000	18	0.52	0.005
4	0.51	0.003	19	0.58	0.000
5	0.53	0.000	20	0.47	0.000
6	0.58	0.000	21	0.20	0.020
7	0.37	0.000	22	0.56	0.000
8	0.36	0.002	23	0.59	0.000
9	0.37	0.000	24	0.53	0.000
10	0.57	0.000	25	0.62	0.001
11	0.36	0.000	26	0.54	0.000
12	0.29	0.001	27	0.46	0.000
13	0.37	0.000			
14	0.54	0.000			
15	0.48	0.000			

The Reliability of the Tool

The researcher calculated the reliability of the study tool for the students using internal consistency, and this type of reliability indicates the strength of the correlation between the items in the study tool. In order to estimate the internal consistency coefficient, the Cronbach Alpha method was used, as the value of the (alpha) coefficient of total reliability was (0.88), which is a suitable image for the purposes of the study, and it can be trusted.

The Study Variables

Independent Variables

The study included the following independent variables:

- **Gender:** It has two levels (father and mother).
- **Age:** It has four levels: (20_25), (26-30), (31-35), (36 and over).
- **Qualification:** It has three levels: (Tawjihi or less), (Diploma), (Bachelor) and (Masters and above).
- **Income:** It has four levels: - (less than 1500), (1500 - 2500), (2501 - 3500), and (more than 3500).

Dependent variable: It is the estimates of the study sample members on the study tool.

Study Application Procedures

After confirming the validity and reliability of the test, and determining the study population and its sample, the researcher coordinated with the municipal councils; in order to obtain permission and allow him to implement the study, the study was implemented in the second semester of the year (2013/2014), the researcher followed the process of collecting data and entering it into the computer, and the data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Statistical Processors

- The main question was answered using arithmetic means, standard deviations, and percentages.
- The researcher used the (Independent T-Test) to answer the first question in identifying the differences between the sexes.
- The researcher used arithmetic averages and then One-way analysis variance to answer the second question according to the educational qualification variable.
- The researcher used arithmetic averages and then One-way analysis variance to answer the third question according to the age variable.

- Arithmetic averages, then One-way analysis of variance, as well as the (LSD) test for dimensional comparisons between arithmetic averages according to the income variable.
- The researcher used arithmetic averages and then One-way analysis variance according to the variable number of family members.

The Study Results and Discussion

In order to determine the reality of the family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in the city of Tulkarm through the arithmetic averages of the responses; The range was calculated for the quintuple scale ($5 - 1 = 4$), then the range was divided by the number of categories, in order to determine the length of the category ($4 / 5 = 0.80$), so the first category was ($1 + 0.80 = 1.80$), then (0.80) is added) for each category as follows (Abu Dalal, 2010; Nasser, 2010):

- An arithmetic mean (1-1.80), or a percentage (less than 36%), indicates a very low score.
- An arithmetic mean (1.81 -2.60), or a percentage (36.1% - 52%), indicates a low degree.
- An arithmetic mean (2.61 - 3.40), or a percentage (52.1% - 68%) indicating an average score.
- An arithmetic mean (3.41 - 4.20), or a percentage (68.1% - 84%) indicates a significant degree.
- An arithmetic mean (4.21 - 5), or a percentage (more than 84%) indicates a very large degree.

The Results of the Study

Results related to the main question: What is the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab.

To answer this question, the averages and standard deviations of the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites were extracted from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab, in all fields of study and the total degree as follows:

Arranging the fields of study according to the total score for each domain:

The researcher used the arithmetic averages of the items on the total scores of the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites to arrange the domains of study as shown in Table (3).

Table 3: Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, degree and order of the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites according to the responses of the study sample members

N	The dimension	N of items	The upper limit of the mean	Arithmetic average in terms of item	STD	Relative importance	Level	Impact degree
3	Psychological domain	11	3.58	3.14	0.78	1	First	Moderate
1	The family relations domain	7	3.27	2.98	0.79	2	Second	Moderate
2	Cultural domain	9	4.81	2.53	0.71	3	Third	Low
Total degree				2.88	0.62	57.7	----	Moderate

It is clear from Table (3) that the total degree of the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the parents' point of view in the city of Sahab was few, as the total percentage of the average responses of the respondents on all items for all fields was (57.7%).

The order of the fields according to the impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab was as follows:

First rank: The psychological domain.

Second rank: The family relations domain.

Third rank: The cultural domain.

This result was in conflict with the study (Michel Vanson, 2010) and the study (Sari, 2008), which showed the negative impact of social networking sites on family relationships, and the researcher believes that the reason behind the low impact of social networking sites on family relationships is the presence of awareness among families in the city of Sahab towards the negative impact of these sites on family relationships that reduce communication between family members. Despite the benefits of social media and the emergence of modern applications, it has led to the separation of kinship and reduced visits between friends and family members. She added that it is noticeable during family meetings that there are those who are preoccupied with these applications and neglect those around them, and these applications waste time, but the user determines how to use these applications, but users waste a lot of time communicating with friends, monitoring their friends' updates and responding to their comments, in addition to spending a lot of time in useless games. Also, the absence of censorship, the lack of responsibility of some users, the large number of rumors, the exaggeration

of the transfer of events, some discussions that depart from mutual respect, the lack of acceptance of the other opinion, the wasting of time in moving between pages and files without benefit, and browsing websites; This leads to isolating young people and adolescents from their family reality and their participation in the events held by society. It also led to the emergence of a new language among young people - between Arabic and English - which would weaken our Arabic language and lose its identity, and lead to a lack of privacy that leads to moral, psychological and material damages.

Results related to the first question: Does the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites differ from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab according to the gender of the parent?

In order to answer this question, arithmetic averages, standard deviations, percentages, and the degree of impact were used, and the tables (5,4,3) show this, while Table (4) shows the arrangement of the fields according to the degree of impact.

With regard to the psychological domain, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations were as shown in Table:(4)

Table 4: Arithmetic averages, percentages, and the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in Sahab city, according to the family relations domain

N	Item	Mean	STD	Percentage	Impact degree
1	My sons spend most of their time browsing social media.	2.72	1.32	%54.0	Moderate
2	Social media is influencing the lifestyle of my children.	2.79	1.38	%55.2	Moderate
3	Participation in social networking sites reduces communication between family members.	3.10	1.44	%56.3	Moderate
4	Social media allows me to find out what affects my children's mind.	3.01	1.37	%60.9	Moderate
5	I organize my children's use of social networking sites.	2.82	1.41	%56.4	Moderate
6	Communication between family members takes place through social networking sites.	3.12	1.46	%62.5	Moderate
7	Preoccupation with social networking sites leads to neglect in performing homework.	3.11	1.13	%56.2	Moderate
8	Family members' use of social networking sites makes direct communication with family members a difficult process.	3.13	1.25	%62.7	Moderate
9	The use of social networking sites by family members negatively affects the organization of group meals at home.	3.27	1.27	%65.3	Moderate
10	The use of social networking sites causes problems between spouses.	2.79	1.38	%55.9	Moderate
11	My sons communicate with their friends on social media more than they do with the rest of the family.	3.22	1.25	%57.7	Moderate
Total degree		3.51	0.816	59.6	

It is clear from Table (4) that the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations according to the field of family relations was average on all items, as the percentage of respondents' responses to these items was (54.0%-57.7%), as for the total degree of the impact of the field of family relations, it was of a small degree, as the value of the average percentage of the respondents' responses to all items was (59.6%), where the degree of the total impact of the field of family relations.

With regard to the cultural field, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations were as shown in Table (5):

Table 5: Arithmetic averages, percentages, and the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations in the city of Sahab according to the cultural field

N	Item	Mean	STD	percentage	Impact degree
12	Social networking sites have contributed to increasing the cultural awareness of its visitors.	4.81	2.11	71.1	High

13	Social media has contributed to increasing the political awareness of its visitors.	2.28	1.064	45.6	Low
14	Social networking sites helped to learn about the cultures of other societies and peoples	2.24	1.13	44.8	Low
15	Social media is a means of exchanging opinions, experiences and ideas	2.19	1.10	43.9	Low
16	Social networking sites help Western cultures dominate Arab cultures	2.79	1.38	55.9	Moderate
17	Social networking sites benefit in the field of study research	2.14	1.11	42.9	Low
18	My children rely heavily on social media for information	2.56	1.22	51.2	Low
19	My children are very interested in communicating with people of different nationalities using social networking sites	3.48	1.39	69.6	High
Total degree		2.53	0.719	50.6	Low

* *Maximum item score (5)*

It is clear from Table (5) that the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations according to the cultural field was high on the item (12,19), where the percentage of respondents' responses to this item was (69.6%), and the degree of impact was small on the items From (13,14,15,17,18), where the percentage of respondents' responses to these paragraphs was between (45.6%, 51.2%), and the degree of impact was medium on paragraph (16), as the percentage of respondents' responses to these paragraphs was between (55.9), and the total degree of the impact of the cultural field was to a small degree, where the value of the average percentage of respondents' responses to all paragraphs was (50.6%), and the total degree of the cultural field conflicted with the study (Al-Shehri, 2013) in terms of the lack of a positive impact on raising cultural awareness through social networking sites.

With regard to the psychological field, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations were as shown in Table (6):

Table 6: Arithmetic averages, percentages, and degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations in the city of Sahab according to the psychological domain

* *Maximum item score (5)*

N	Item	Mean	STD	Percentage	Impact degree
20	Social media has deepened my children's sense of isolation from the reality in which they live	3.31	1.37	66.3	Moderate
21	Social networking sites helped develop my children's personality.	2.96	1.10	59.30	Moderate
22	The use of social networking sites undermines self-confidence.	3.58	1.25	71.7	High
23	Social media works to break the feeling of loneliness.	2.85	1.26	57.13	Moderate
24	My children use social networking sites to escape from worries and problems	3.27	1.34	65.4	Moderate
25	My kids get depressed, nervous, and irritable when they don't use social media	2.93	1.41	58.6	Moderate
26	The use of social networking sites weakens independence and self-reliance	3.13	1.25	62.7	Moderate
27	The use of social media leads to the disintegration of the family	3.12	1.46	62.5	Moderate
Total degree		3.14	0.78	62.9	

It is clear from Table (6) that the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relationships according to the psychological domain was significant on paragraph (22), where the percentage of respondents' responses to this paragraph was (71.76%), and the degree of response was medium on items (20, 21,23,24,25,26,27) where its percentage reached between (62.5%-66.3%), and the total degree of the impact of

the psychological field was moderately, where the value of the average percentage of respondents' responses to all items was (62.9) %).

The results of the study hypotheses

Results related to the first hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in Sahab city according to the gender of the parent.

In order to test the hypothesis, the researcher used an independent t-test for two independent groups, as shown in Table (7).

Table 7: The results of the t-test for the significance of the differences between the averages of the reality of social communication from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab due to the gender variable

Gender	N	Mean	STD	df	t-value	Sig
Male	200	2.87	0.63	430	0.26	0.83
Female	232	2.89	0.62			

* Statistically significant at level ($\alpha \leq 0,05$)

It is clear from Table (7) that the value of the calculated significance level has reached the total score according to the gender variable, respectively (0.83), and these values are greater than the value of the significance level specified for the study ($\alpha \leq 0,05$), that is, we accept the null hypothesis, the researcher believes that the reason for this is that parents, whether they are fathers or mothers, notice when these sites affect their relationship with each other and with the rest of the family, and given the similarity of the conditions in which they live, the parents' real understanding and awareness of the child's treatment, and the parents' awareness and awareness of the child's psychological and emotional needs related to his growth, the development of his idea of himself and his relationship with other people, and the parents' awareness of the child's desires and motives that are behind his behavior, and he may be unable to express them. Teaching the child, the skills that enable him to integrate into society, cooperate with its members, participate in various aspects of activity, and teach him his roles; What he has and what he is, and the way to coordinate between them and his actions in various situations, teach him how to be a useful member of society, and evaluate and control his behavior. However, users waste a lot of time communicating with friends, monitoring their friends' updates and responding to their comments, in addition to spending a lot of time in games. What is not useful is that the children must be persuaded of the necessity of refraining from error without threat, and persuading the boy or girl with good behavior, and indicated that this method is appropriate to make the children return to their senses, and continue on the path of goodness. Parents should not forget the factor of encouragement and moral support, as it has a great role in guiding children, especially during adolescence.

Results related to the second hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relations resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in the city of Sahab according to the educational qualification.

In order to test the hypothesis, the arithmetic averages were extracted according to the educational qualification variable, and then One-Way ANOVA was used to identify the significance of the differences. Tables (8) and (9) showed that:

Table 8: Arithmetic averages of the reality of social communication from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab due to the educational qualification variable

Scientific qualification	N	Mean
Tawjihi and less	16	2.82
	1	
Diploma	88	2.92
Bachelor	140	2.88
Master degree and above	43	3.03

It is evident from Table (8) that there are differences between the arithmetic averages, and in order to find out whether these differences have reached the level of statistical significance, the One-Way ANOVA test was used, and Table (9) shows that:

Table 9: Results of the one-way variance analysis for the significance of the differences between the averages of the reality of social communication from the point of view of parents of students in the city of Sahab due to the educational qualification variable

Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean squares	t-value	Significance level (P)
Between groups	1.30	3	0.43	1.27	0.23
Within groups	107.9	316	0.34		
Total	109.2	319			

It is clear from Table (9) that the value of the significance level calculated from the sample on all fields and on the total degree according to the educational qualification variable of the teacher has reached, respectively (0.074, 0.096, 0.145, 0.284), and these values are greater than the value of the specific significance level, that is, we accept the null hypothesis on these areas and on the overall degree, this means that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance in the impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab, according to the educational qualification variable.

The researcher attributes this result to the fact that the nature of education in most universities depends on the use of technology in education, and therefore many university lecturers communicate with their students through social networking sites to exchange knowledge and deliver assignments or scientific discussions. Social communication from all aspects of religious, social and moral life helped him in directing his children to use these sites in a positive direction and away from negative use. Accordingly, it was found that the higher the educational level of the parents, the greater the positive guidance and counseling.

Results related to the third hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in the city of Sahab according to age.

In order to test the hypothesis, the arithmetic averages were extracted according to the variable of practical experience, and then one-way ANOVA was used to identify the significance of the differences in the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relationships from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab and Tables (10) and (11) shows that:

Table 10: Arithmetic averages of the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab due to the age variable

Age	N	Mean
25_20	78	2.99
30_26	114	2.89
35_31	242	2.83
36 and above	430	2.91

It is evident from Table (10) that there are differences between the arithmetic averages, and in order to find out whether these differences have reached the level of statistical significance, the One-Way ANOVA was used, and Table (11) illustrates this:

Table 11: Results of the one-way variance analysis for the significance of the differences in the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in Sahab city according to the age variable

Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean squares	P value	Significance level (P)
Between groups	0.86	3	0.28	0.84	0.24
Within groups	108.4	316	0.34		
Total	109.2	319			

It is clear from Table (11) that the value of the significance level calculated from the sample on the total degree according to the variable of practical experience has reached (0.24), respectively, and this value is greater than the value of the significance level specified for the study, that is, we accept the null hypothesis on the total degree. This means that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance in

the impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab due to the age variable, the researcher attributes this result to the fact that the progression of the individual's age stage makes him search for continuous social relationships because social networking sites depend on technological development more than on social visits, because sending a message on a social networking site indicates social communication and this appeared in the age group that increases About (36) years old, and that the close age of parents and their children increases the strength of the relationship and understanding between them, and this makes parents interact with their children through social networking sites, because parents are contemporary to social networking sites, which were a source of communication in the early stages of their social life.

Results related to the fourth hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in Sahab city according to the family's income.

In order to test the hypothesis, the arithmetic averages were extracted according to the variable of the type of specialization, and then one-way ANOVA was used to identify the significance of the differences in the degree of the impact of social networking sites on family relationships from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab, due to the income variable and Tables (12) and (13) show that:

Table 12: Arithmetic averages of the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab due to the income variable

Income	N	Mean
1500 or less	88	2.75
2500_1500	155	2.84
3500_2501	102	2.94
More than 3500	86	3.02

It is clear from Table (12) that there are differences between the arithmetic averages, and in order to find out whether these differences have reached the level of statistical significance, the One-Way ANOVA test was used, and Table (13) illustrates this:

Table 13: Results of one-way variance analysis for the significance of differences in the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relationships from the point of view of parents in Sahab city due to the income variable

Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	P value	Significance level (P)
Between groups	2.88	3	0.95	2.84	0.03
Within groups	106.4	316	0.33		
Total	109.2	319			

** Statistically significant at significance level ($\alpha=0.05$)

It is clear from Table (13) that the value of the significance level calculated from the sample, the total degree of the impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab, according to the income variable, amounted to (0.03) and these values are less than the value of the significance level specified for the study, that is, we reject the null hypothesis, which means that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance in the impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab according to the income variable.

Table 14: The results of the LSD test for dimensional comparisons to indicate the differences in the degree of the impact of social networking sites on family relationships from the point of view of parents in Sahab city according to the income variable (total score)

Comparisons	Mean	Less than 1500	2500_1500	3500_2501	More than 3500
Less than 1500	2.75			*0.18	
2500_1500	2.84				*0.18
3500_2501	2.94				

More than 3500	3.02	*0.26			
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It is evident from the results of Table (14) that there are differences in the degree of impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab between (2501_3500) and less than 1500 in favor of (2501_3500), and between more than 3500 and less than 1500 in favor of less than 1500 And between (1500-2500) and more than 3500 in favor (1500-2500), the researcher believes that the reason for this is due to the fact that the increase in parents' income leads to the availability of modern social media technologies in various forms and types, even if their costs are high, and that is their belief that it helps them to be distracted from leaving the house, which can sow social problems at the neighborhood level or belief the neighborhood can earn him some improper behavior or words, so he seeks to provide each family member with his device that he can use for social communication to make most of his time on those sites, which often the family is busy from following them because of obtaining extra income to provide their technological requirements so that Social networking sites become the first teacher of the behavior of all family members, which are often negative if they leave the family control circle.

Results related to the fifth hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences in the reality of family relationships resulting from social networking sites from the point of view of the students' parents in Sahab city according to the family's income.

In order to test the hypothesis, the arithmetic averages were extracted according to the variable of family members, and then one-way analysis of variance (One-Way ANOVA) was used to identify the significance of the differences in the degree of social networking sites on family relationships from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab according to the variable of family members and Tables ((15) and (16) show that:

Number of family members	N	Mean
Less than 4 members	12 1	2.93
4-6 members	20 0	2.88
6 members or more	1111	2.84

It is evident from Table (15) that there are differences between the arithmetic averages, and in order to find out whether these differences have reached the level of statistical significance, the One-Way ANOVA test was used, and Table (16) shows this:

Table 16: Results of the one-way analysis of variance for the significance of the differences in the degree of the impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in the city of Sahab due to the variable of family members

Source of variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	P value	Significance level (P)
Between groups	1.2	3	0.42	1.23	0.23
Within groups	108	316	0.34		
Total	109.2	319			

* Statistically significant at significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

It is clear from Table (16) that the value of the significance level calculated from the sample in all fields and on the total degree according to the variable of practical experience amounted to (0.428, 0.178, 0.297, 0.296), and these values are greater than the value of the significance level specified for the study ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) i.e. We accept the null hypothesis on these areas, and on the total degree, which means that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the impact of social networking sites on family relations from the point of view of parents in Sahab city due to the variable number of family members, the researcher believes that the goal of using social networking sites is not affected by the number of family members, but by the availability of technological means and the economic situation of the family, because the more technological means are available, the more they help the use of social networking sites. Its members alternately use devices for social communication purposes to build social relationships. Therefore, families that do not have a number of devices commensurate with the number of their family members allocate time for each individual for social communication, but does he use that time in a positive way.

Recommendations

In light of the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

- Removing the barriers between parents and children, which helps children from their parents' experiences in life and guide them in order to overcome the psychological difficulties they encounter in their daily lives.

- The lack of excessive technological means due to the availability of high income because it exposes children to the risk of irrational use of technology devices.
- Consolidating all the meanings of humanity and ways to maintain the heat of social and family relations through the educational level they possess.
- Instilling a culture of dialogue in the hearts of children from a young age and accustoming them to dialogue, which will reflect positively on their attitudes and behavior in their dealings with others in society, regardless of the number of family members.
- Rational use of social networking sites, regardless of the age stage of the individual.
- Conducting more studies on social networking sites related to family relations at the level of Palestine in general and for different age groups in particular.

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